

Revolutionizing Beauty: The Evolution of Biomaterials in Cosmetics

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ABSTRACT

The use of biomaterials in the cosmetic industry has gained substantial attention due to their biocompatibility, multifunctionality and unique properties. This review focuses on the use of biomaterials such as hyaluronic acid, gelatin, collagen, hydrogel and silicone particularly in hair, skin and personal care products. There is increasing demand for effective and safe delivery of bioactive ingredients in formulation of cosmetic products. Biomaterials improve the skin health as well enhance aesthetic appeal of the products leading to advancement in biotechnology and material science. Significant research findings highlight the effectiveness of these biomaterials in reducing wrinkles, promote wound healing, enhancing skin hydration and skin elasticity by stimulating cell regeneration and reducing trans epidermal water content. Biomaterials have multifunctional properties such as anti-oxidant and anti-inflammatory effects that plays a crucial role in treating skin conditions like eczema, acne and improving skin aesthetic. The increasing emphasis on sustainability in cosmetics will also drive research into eco-friendly, renewable and biodegradable biomaterials. Biomaterials potentially reduces the impact of synthetic ingredients on the environment. In future, the development of bioengineered and more advanced materials that can mimic the natural function and structure of the skin can be researched. Advances in nanotechnology, tissue engineering and 3D bioprinting can aid in creation of enhanced delivery system and high-performance cosmetic products. Increasing incorporation of growth factors, bioactive peptides and plant-based alternatives in cosmetics are more likely to enhance appeal and efficacy of biomaterials in the coming years. These biomaterials hold promise for more sustainable, efficacious and innovative cosmetic solutions.

Keywords: Cosmetics, Biomaterials, Polysaccharides, Skin care, Anti-aging.

I. INTRODUCTION

Biomaterials or bio-based materials can be defined as the materials that are extracted from a living biological organism and can be obtained by artificial as well as natural processing [1]. Biomaterials are being increasingly used in various industries of cosmetics and personal care products in order to achieve environment friendly business model around the globe [2]. Increasing aesthetic demands of the aging global population led to the desire to appear healthy and youthful [3]. Biomaterials are used as raw materials in medicine, cosmetics, food, textile, electrical, pharmaceutical, personal care and packaging industries [4]. Biomaterials are derived from natural compounds such as animals, plants, macro or micro-organisms, free from any kind of chemical compounds [5]. The biomaterials used in the formulation of cosmetic products are free from synthetic hazardous ingredients that plays a vital role in the reducing the harm to both humans and environment [6]. The personal care and cosmetic industry provide a wide variety of products including the day and night oils, lotions, creams, hair-dyes, nail polishes, lip care products, tonics, cleansers, spray serums, etc and many more products that are used daily by almost every individual [7]. As there is an increase in use of social-media and technology, there is an increased craze of chemical free and natural products where people are becoming more concerned towards their health and well-being [8]. Personal care products and cosmetics industries are significantly affected by this growing trends. Organic, eco-friendly and bio-based products are the most accepted concepts of the current growing market including organic, green and bio-cosmetic, receiving much importance because of the shifting preferences [9]. The bio-cosmetic market is worth more than 178 billion dollars across the globe and it is estimated to grow about 15.6% that is around 205 billion dollars till 2030 [10]. The primary cause for increase in the market is the financing for the production of innovative biomaterials, government grants, their increased prevalence in medical field and plastic surgery [11].

II. HISTORY OF USES OF BIOMATERIALS

Year	Uses	Description
Ancient times (Pre-19 th century)	Raw biomaterials	Bone and Ivory implements were used for fixing the broken limbs by ancient Egyptians [12].
19 th century	Synthetic materials	1.Gutta-Percha: is a latex material derived from Palaquium tree, used in root canal filling because of its ability to get moulded [13]. 2.Silver/Gold: These metals were used for dental fillings, crowns and inlays because of its resistance to corrosion and durability [14].
1950s	Silicone implants	1.Silicone implants: used for breasts and facial implants in cosmetic procedures [15].
1980s	Tissue engineering	Foundation of creating bioengineered organs and tissues in cases of organ transplant and shortages [16].
2000s	Nanotechnology	Implementation of nanomaterials for imaging techniques, drug delivery systems and diagnostic tools [17].
2010s	3D Bioprinting	Creation of complex organ models and tissue structures [18].
2020s	Biocompatible fillers	Made from biomaterials like hyaluronic acid or calcium hydroxyapatite the skin, reduces wrinkles and enhances facial aesthetics tightens [19].

TABLE I: History of uses of biomaterials

III. IMPORTANCE OF BIOMATERIALS IN COSMETICS

The use of biomaterials has brought changes, to industries, including the beauty sector. Incorporating biomaterials into beauty products does not enhance their effectiveness but also addresses the growing consumer demand for sustainability and natural components [20]. The significance of biomaterials in cosmetics is evident in aspects like skin compatibility, environmental impact and innovation [21]. Unlike compounds many biomaterials are biocompatible reducing the risk of skin irritation or allergic reactions [22]. Natural elements such, as collagen, hyaluronic acid and chitosan mimic the body's substances to enhance functionality and absorption [23]. Hyaluronic acid is preferred for its ability to retain the moisture, that is why it is commonly used as an ingredient in antiaging products and moisturizers [24]. Other biomaterials such as collagen plays a vital role in reducing wrinkles and maintaining skin elasticity. Because of an increase in environmental damage by synthetic chemicals and microplastics in the personal care products, both consumers and manufacturers are turning their products into a greener option [25]. Biomaterials are majorly derived from biodegradable and renewable resources, helps in reducing the environmental hazard caused by cosmetics. For example, plant oil is considered as an alternative to the harmful petrochemical ingredients damaging the skin as well as has a harmful impact on the environment [26]. Biomaterials derived from natural sources fulfil those requirements by offering a safe and clean alternative to synthetic materials [27]. Seaweed, green tea extract and aloe vera gel have no or less effect on both skin and environment. Prebiotics and probiotics are added to the personal care products to support the microbiome, kill harmful bacteria, balance beneficial bacteria in the skin and reduce inflammation [28]. Hence, biomaterials play most important role in cosmetic industries because of their environmental benefits, safety, their ability to support skin health, improve product performance and contribute to sustainable practices that helps them developing effective and valuable cosmetic products [29].

IV. TYPES OF BIOMATERIALS IN COSMETICS

Biomaterials plays a key role in the cosmetic industry by offering normal and feasible options in contrast to engineered parts [30]. These biomaterials are obtained from different natural sources to upgrade their productivity and make sustainable and beneficial items in beauty care products [31]. Biomaterials have turned into a noticeable focus in the skincare business because of their flexibility and viability. Their incorporation into skincare items is driven by their biocompatibility, capacity to cooperate decidedly with the skin, and potential to further develop skin wellbeing [32].

Polysaccharides are the most widely recognized biomaterials utilized in the therapeutic area. Chitosan is a biomaterial obtained from chitin that is known for its antibacterial and filmshaping properties [33]. It works on the productivity of skincare items by fighting microorganisms and shaping a defensive layer on the skin [34]. Hyaluronic acid is a normally happening polysaccharide that is perceived for its capacity to hold moisture by making it a typical fixing in saturating medicines like serums and salves [35].

Proteins and peptides are likewise key biomaterials utilized in the restorative area. Collagen is a protein that gives structure and is normally remembered for hostile to maturing medicines [36]. It assists with lessening wrinkles and further develop skin adaptability. The critical fixing in creams and covers is known for its ability to re-establish the skin's regular collagen level [37]. Accordingly, bioengineered peptides are progressively being utilized to treat normal skin problems like dark circles while additionally further developing collagen creation [38]. They likewise help to stimulate collagen development, increase skin flexibility, hydration and immovability, decrease irritation and furthermore have wound healing properties [39]. Peptides are to a great extent utilized in haircare, lotions, serums and eye creams. They are fit for penetrating into the skin layer making them viable in fixing different skin problems [40].

Lipids and oils obtained from plants and animals play an essential role in superficial industry where they are profoundly known for their mitigating and hydrating impacts [41]. Oils from plants, for example, argan, coconut and jojoba protect the skin and keeps it hydrating because they are rich in nutrients and unsaturated fats [42]. These oils act as a skin's obstruction and furthermore prevents moisture from getting away. Squalene is a lipid extracted from shark live oil and olives has an outstanding moisturizing qualities and skin-penetrating capabilities [43]. Lipids like rosehip oil, vitamin E and oils helps in neutralizing free radicals that protects the skin from getting damaged [44]. Lipids also helps in stability and increasing the shelf life of the self-care products. Oils and lipids used in cosmetic products include coconut oil, olive oil, beeswax, carnauba wax, lecithin, linoleic acid, etc. They are used in cosmetic products such as lip balms, serums, lotions, creams, etc [45].

Plant extracts and botanicals contain a variety of beneficial skincare components such as alkaloids, flavonoids and tannins [46]. Aloe vera is well known for its moisturizing and calming qualities have made it demanding for inflamed and sensitive skin [47]. Green tea extract is known for its anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties protects the skin against harmful environment and minimizes aging symptoms [48]. It also has antimicrobial properties helps protecting the skin from risk of infections and improves the appearance and texture of the skin [49]. Plant resources possess beneficial properties that are highly preferred because of their efficacy and safety. Superior properties like antiaging, antiinflammatory, anti-oxidation, moisturizing makes them a key ingredient in sunscreen, face masks and serum [50].

Synthetic polymers have a wide range of application in the biomedical industries as an implantable material since 1940 [51]. Their excellency in biocompatibility and mechanical properties makes them suitable for certain biomedical [52]. Synthetic polymers include silicone in the development of contact lenses, urinary catheters, lubricants, medical implants, constructive gel fillers, etc [53]. Silicone also has a variety of applications in skin care where it is used in the formulation of moisturizers, creams and lotions where it aims in promoting smooth fine lines and hydration [54]. It also promotes skin elasticity, reduces scarring and works as an antiaging compound [55].

V. BIOMATERIALS USED IN COSMETIC INDUSTRIES

Fig.1. Biomaterials used in cosmetic industries

A. Gelatin

Gelatin is known to be a versatile biopolymer found in connective tissue, bones and skin of animals specifically from skin of pig referred to as type A gelatin whereas gelatin derived from beef skin is called as type B gelatin [56]. Gelatin is a solid, colourless, turbid, odourless powder stored at 15-25°C and has a gelling temperature of 22.5°C. It is soluble in acetic acid, water, ether and polycyclic alcohols [57]. It primarily comprises of mixtures of proteins and peptides derived from partial hydrolysis of collagen [58]. Gelatin also comprises of a small amount of carbohydrates, water and minerals. Gelatin is degraded easily in the environment but it can promote protein denaturation above 40°C and can be dissolved at high temperatures if kept for longer durations [59]. Gelatin comprises of hydroxyproline (10%), high amount of amino acid proline (12%) and hydroxylysine (0.5%). The concentration of hydroxyproline and proline may vary depending on its origin. For example, fish gelatin has a lower concentration of amino acids as compared to other mammals that worsens the mechanical property and stability of gelatin preventing the use of fish gelatin in personal care industry [60]. Certain edible cosmetics such as flavoured glosses, lipsticks and lip balms contains gelatin that helps in enhancing the texture and glossiness of the products [61]. It is also found in some temporary hair colours forming a gel-like consistency that helps adhere the colour to the hair strands [62]. Gelatin acts as a binder, emulsifier, thickening agent and film-forming agent. The constituents of gelatin adhere together during the product formation [63]. It also adds to luxurious and smooth consistency of lotions and creams and also it is well recognized for its smoothening and moisturizing properties in serums and moisturizers [64].

Benefits of Gelatin

Skin Hydration: Gelatin forms a thin film when applied topically and acts as a barrier on the surface of the skin [65]. The thin film prevents the loss of water from the skin referred to as trans epidermal water

loss (TEWL) and keeps the skin hydrated for a longer duration [66]. In a study carried out in United States of America, 106 women were given pork gelatin supplements on regular basis for 84 days and 100 women were given fish gelatin supplements. All of those women consuming pork gelatin experienced 28% increase in skin moisture whereas women consuming fish gelatin experienced 12% increase in skin moisture [67].

Wound Healing: Hydrogels composed of gelatin has been reported to enhance wound healing [68]. Gelatin promotes haemostasis, vascular regeneration, epithelial tissue regeneration and anti-infection enhancing the process of chronic wound healing [69]. Pure gelatin act as a carrier molecule used for bioactive dressings that enhances wound healing without causing any side-effects [70].

Anti-Aging: Gelatin hydrolysate has been known to be effective against UV rays that inhibits the activity and expression of matrix metalloproteinases [71]. Gelatin enhances the production of new collagen into the skin [72]. The face masks made by gelatin stimulates the growth of collagen, binds to the oil, dead cells, dirt and toxins and exfoliates the skin when the mask is peeled off [73].

Applications in personal care industries

Fig. 2. Applications of gelatin in personal care industry

B. Hydrogel

Hydrogels are hydrophilic polymers, widely used in skin care and cosmetic products and can be extracted from polysaccharides present in plants [77]. The unique properties of hydrogels include elasticity, high water retention capacity, biocompatibility and softness has drawn the attention of researchers in the personal care industry [78]. Naturally derived hydrogels are usually composed of polysaccharides containing single sugar molecules linked together or protein chains. Hydrogel exhibits a great potential as a constituent in cosmetic and skin care preparation [79]. Hydrogels obtained from natural sources are easily available and inexpensive [80].

Major sources of Hydrogel

Agar: It is a natural polymer composed of sulphate groups and galactose polymer, extracted from the cell wall of red marine algae [81]. Based on its chemical properties and stability, it has a wide range of applications in hair conditioners, skin moisturizer, facial masks, deodorants, creams, shampoos and lotions [82].

Alginate: It is obtained from brown algae and is also known as alginic acid. Calcium salt present in alginate makes them suitable for forming surface films because of its high swelling ratio that retain the skin's moisture [83]. Alginate has the ability to stabilize oil phase cosmetics due to their solubility in water. They can soften the skin and hydrate it so they have been incorporated in anti-wrinkle products and moisturizers [84]. Alginate contributes to wound healing process by exhibiting antibacterial activity preventing the wound from drying and enhances the wound healing process [85]. Calcium sulphate and sodium alginate are typically used in beauty treatments as key ingredients in face masks [86].

Glycogen: Glycogen is a branched polysaccharide is known for its skin conditioning property [87]. Refined glycogen is known to have anti-aging effect by protecting against sun damage. It is for this reason that glycogen is typically used in the formulation of sun screen, body wash and shampoos [88].

Benefits of Hydrogel

Fig.3. Benefits of hydrogels

C. Collagen

Collagen is a triple helix structure comprises of three basic amino acids: Glycine, proline and hydroxyproline [89]. Each amino acid has specific function in the collagen. Collagen as a biomaterial, is extracted from porcine, bovine or equine, known to be the standard biological sources [90]. They have also been extracted from organisms like Yeast, E. coli, mammalian cell culture and plants. Collagen has wide distribution in tissues and excellent biocompatibility that makes it suitable to be used as a biomaterial. It is considered to be a building block for skin, tendons, ligaments, hair, nails and muscles [91].

Applications of Collagen

Anti-Aging: Collagen production decreases with increasing age, giving rise to sagging skin and wrinkles [92]. Oral supplements or topical collagen helps in improving hydration, skin elasticity, reduce wrinkles and roughness [93]. Oral collagen supplements are typically powders and pills sold under the name of collagen peptides, hydrolysed collagen or hydrosylate [94]. Retinoids (Vitamin A) enhance the production of collagen and are known to reduce fine lines, wrinkles and age spots [95].

Hydration and Moisturization: Collagen is a water-soluble component that has the ability to enhance elasticity and skin hydration [96]. It is known to be derived from hydrolysed collagen and applied topically where it forms film on the skin and provides skin tightening effect. Collagen is majorly used in serums, moisturizers and lotions providing more youthful and smoother complexion to the skin [97].

Hair care: By age, collagen production decreases in the body. Collagen supplements have been known to contribute to longer, thicker hair growth, healthy structure of hair follicle and a reduction in gray hair. Collagen gels and creams, when applied directly to the scalp, the gray hairs appear less dry and appears more blacker [98]. Topical products and supplements of collagen can maintain healthy level of hydration and repair split ends [99]. Some collagen supplements also contain biotin which is beneficial for maintenance of healthy hair [100].

Nail care: Type I collagen is found to be essential for maintenance of strong, healthy, flexible and moisturized nails and is the most important collagen with respect to overall nail growth and appearance [101]. Collagen functions as a glue that holds the keratin present in the nails together. It prevents the nails from breaking easily and becoming brittle [102]. Fish collagen hydrosylate is considered to be the

best collagen supplement for nail care. Certain products such as nail conditioners, oils and serum consists of collagen as a key compound [103].

Lip care: Collagen has been extensively used in lip care. It is known to reverse deterioration by providing structure, elasticity and shape to the lips [104]. Collagen containing lip masks are also developed to treat thinning, fine lines and wrinkles, essential for adding collagen serums deep into the lips [105]. Topical collagen can also plump the lips but the lip masks provide pout puffing effects and temporary hydration [106].

Skin care: Increased elastin and collagen enhances regeneration of the skin by reducing stretch marks and improving appearance of the skin [107]. Microneedling is a therapy where tiny needles are poked to target the dermis layer of the skin, where stretch marks are formed, which triggers collagen production [108]. Collagen injections cause the skin to heal faster and makes it appear smoother [109].

D. Hyaluronic acid (HA)

Hyaluronic acid (HA) is linear polysaccharide having a high molecular weight composed of N-acetyl glucosamine and d-glucuronic acid through the exchange of β -1,3 and β -1,4 [110]. HA was first discovered in the eyes of the cow and then later found in skin, lungs, kidneys, muscles and brain of humans [111]. It is a type of polysaccharide with beneficial and unique properties for biomedical applications [112]. HA fillers are considered to be an effective tool for wrinkles, skin rejuvenation and lip augmentation. Skin aging is progressive, complex and irreversible process followed by morphological, biochemical and biophysical changes in the body [113]. HA has become the most preferred choice because of its ease of administration, high efficacy and safety profile as well as low toxicity presenting itself as a gold standard among fillers in the list of cosmetic dermal fillers [114]. HA also acts as a wetting agent in contact lens helping with dry eye therapy. HA has a wide range of applications in moisturizing cream, lotions, gels, serum, conditioner, nail drops, etc [115].

Applications of Hyaluronic acid

Fig.4. Applications of HA

E. Silicone

Silicones are derived from the element silicon which are produced by the conversion of quartz into silicon further reacting with methyl chloride producing chlorosilanes [125]. These chlorosilanes react with silanols and water where silanols are converted into dimethicone, cyclomethicone and other silicones that are used to produce cosmetic products [126]. Silicones are polymers with unique

properties that are added to the personal care and cosmetic product formulation [127]. Silicones act as thickeners, moisturizers, emulsifiers, pearlizers and conditioners. Silicones are added to neutralize irritation caused by harsh surfactants [128]. The most common silicones used in cosmetics are alkyl methyl siloxanes, silicone elastomers, silicone fluids, silicone gum blends, silicone emulsions and silicone polyethers [129].

Applications of Silicone

Hair care

i) Conditioners and Shampoos: Silicones were first added to the hair care products to improve hair lustre, softness and provide protective coat to the hair [130]. The most common silicone found in conditioners and shampoos include dimethiconol, dimethicone, cyclomethicone, amodimethicone, bis-aminopropyl, anionic silicones and siloxy silicates [131]. Silicone improves curl retention, improves hair feel, making them smooth and softer. It also provides increased protection to hair colour, helping against heat damage, providing moisturization, increasing lustre and shine and enhancing the hair volume [132].

ii) Heat Protectants: Silicone serves as a protective barrier by reducing the need of extreme heat and achieve desired straightening effects [133]. Incorporation of silicone in hair sprays helps people achieve desired hairstyle without harming the hair [134]. By introducing functionalized silicone, consumers can have easier and safer thermal hair straightening experience. Frizz occurs when hair lacks moisture and becomes dry [135]. Silicone based heat protectants plays a vital role in controlling hair frizz. Moisture retaining property of silicone makes the hair smoother and manageable [136].

Makeup

i) Primers: Primer has a mattifying effect that helps in smoothening fine lines and blurs the pores helping the foundation to stay for a longer time [137]. Silicone primers created smooth surface on the face allowing the makeup to set on the skin more evenly and smoothly [138]. There is another type of primer known as oil-based primer suitable for the people with dry skin. Oil primer ensures that the skin is moisturized and nourished and has no dry patches [139].

ii) Foundations: Silicone based foundations are more mattifying as compared to waterbased foundations that are useful for the people having oily skin-type [140]. Silicone foundations are well known for their long-lasting full glam looks. These foundations are suitable options for covering fine lines, wrinkles and visible pores [141].

iii) Silicone Fillers : Silicone injections are also known as dermal fillers that are found to be incorporated into the tissue to change the body's shape [142]. There are different injections of silicone that can temporarily alter appearance of fine lines and wrinkles. A person may need to repeat the process in regular intervals to maintain desired effects [143].

iv) Silicone Implants: Silicone gel-filled implant has a rubber shell made up of polysiloxane such as polydiphenylsiloxane and polymethylsiloxane filled with fixed amount of silicone gel [144]. Silicone gel-filled implants may vary in shape, shell surface, shell thickness and volume [145]. Silicone implants have shorter operation time as compared to autologous grafts [146]. Silicone implants resist tissue ingrowth and become a fibrous capsule that helps in maintaining the position of the implant. Silicone implants are also widely used in medical devices because of their bio durable and biocompatible property [147]. Silicone breast implants have an outer covering filled with silicone gel having different sizes and also have textured or smooth shells. Silicone breast implants are approved for breast augmentation for women above 22 years of age [148]. Breast implants are done in people who wanted to reconstruct their breasts after cancer surgery or in people who want larger breasts [149].

Fig.5.Types of silicone implants

VI. SAFETY AND REGULATIONS

Country	Regulatory organization	Regulations and Sections	Applicability to cosmetic products
INDIA	CDSCO (Central Drugs Standard Control Organization)	Drugs and Cosmetics Act, 1940 Drugs and Cosmetic Rules, 1945	Safety, labelling and ingredient regulation of cosmetics [154].
SOUTH KOREA	MFDS (Ministry of Food and Drug Safety)	Enforcement Rule of the Cosmetic Act	-Specific guidelines for functional cosmetics, which include sunscreens, whitening products, anti-wrinkle products, and more [155].
UNITED STATES	FDA (Food and Drug Administration)	Federal Food, Drug, and Cosmetic Act (FD&C Act) 21 CFR 700-740	- Cosmetic product safety, labeling, and adulteration - Regulation of color additives and cosmetic ingredients [156].
AUSTRALIA	NICNAS (National Industrial Chemicals Notification and Assessment Scheme)	Industrial Chemicals (Notification and Assessment) Act 1989 Cosmetics Standard 2022	- Pre-market assessment of ingredients - Regulation of cosmetic chemicals used in personal care and cosmetic products [157].

TABLE II : Safety and regulations of biomaterials in India, South Korea, United states and Australia

VII. LIMITATIONS OF BIOMATERIALS IN COSMETICS

1. **Cost:** Purification and extraction of high-quality biomaterials can be expensive. High levels of biocompatibility are required in order to derive any product from biomaterials. As a result, they tend to be more expensive to manufacture and commercialize [158].
2. **Safety:** Many people are found to be allergic or sensitive towards biomaterials like hyaluronic acid or collagen [159]. Collagen extracted from animal sources may trigger immune response in some individuals [160].
3. **Shelf-life and Stability:** Biomaterials like gelatin and silk are more prone to degradation when exposed to certain temperatures [161]. It causes microbial contamination leading to high sensitivity to enzyme degradation if not stored at optimum temperature and may cause allergic reactions [162]. Anti-aging property of collagen is diminished by the enzymes present on the skin surface [163].
4. **Environmental challenges:** Biomaterials like chitosan, elastin, fibrin, silicone, etc are nonbiodegradable and may cause harm to the environment [164]. Such synthetically derived biomaterials face various challenges for their disposal and can persist in the environment. Silicone being non-biodegradable may cause its accumulation in the environment [165].
5. **Quality control and Consistency:** Biomaterials derived from natural sources vary in their composition depending on the methods of extraction and sources affecting efficacy and consistency of the product. E.g. Purity and molecular weight of collagen varies, affecting their functions in skin care formulations [166].
6. **Limited customization:** Biomaterials derived from natural sources have certain limitations when compared to synthetic ones. It becomes difficult to maintain colour, texture, consistency and flexibility [167].
7. **Slow absorption rate:** Biomaterials like collagen and hyaluronic acid may not penetrate deep into the skin layer without using specific delivery systems [168]. Large molecules of these biomaterials are unable to cross the skin barrier, reducing anti-aging effect [169].
8. **Difficulty in mass production:** Production of large quantities of biomaterials while maintaining the functionality and quality is a complex process [170]. It requires specialization in purification, harvesting and extraction process for scaling up mass production [171].

VIII. CONCLUSION

Despite the associated limitations, biomaterials function as promising therapeutic materials in the field of cosmetics [172]. Additional investigations are needed to focus on providing biocompatibility, shelf-life and long-lasting effect [173]. Globally, hydrogel, collagen, gelatin, hyaluronic acid and silicone are the most frequently used biomaterials [174]. Due to their applications, efficacy and economic impact they take away the crown for being the best biomaterials. Hyaluronic acid emerges as a frontrunner in terms of versatility, financial impact, efficacy and consumer demands [175]. Globally the market of hyaluronic acid is approximately 15 billion USD and there is an increasing demand for products constituting HA such as anti-aging creams, moisturizers, dermal fillers, etc [176]. It has the ability to boost elasticity and hydrate the skin deeply, making it a key constituent of skin care products. Countries like Japan and South Korea are greatly contributing in this growing market of HA [177]. Globally, the market of collagen is expected to surpass 9 billion USD by 2028 with its wide range of use in food products and supplements [178]. Collagen has been a competitor to HA because of its application in anti-aging product. However, its use in vegan alternatives limits it among the consumers [179]. The market of hydrogel is expected to surpass 32 billion USD by 2030. Its majority of use is in medical and cosmetic use is still emerging [180]. Its use in cosmetics is still being evaluated. Global revenue of gelatin will reach around 6 billion USD by 2028 [181]. Silicone market has a value of over 20 billion USD. It has a moderate growth as compared to hyaluronic acid [182]. Because of its increased scrutiny over environmental impact, the industry is trying to shift towards more natural alternative [183]. Hydrogels hold the potential for innovative delivery systems of the active ingredients along with its applications in cooling and hydrating skin treatments [184]. The global hydrogel market will be approximately worth 32 billion USD by 2030. It is difficult to source biomaterials because they can vary according to factors like soil, climate and harvest cycles [185]. Biomaterials can be sensitive to pH, moisture, temperature [186]. Another challenge for cosmetic industry is to create a balance between economic and sustainability. With growing demand, biomaterials offer biocompatible solutions and an exciting frontier for the cosmetic industry. Integration of these naturally derived biomaterials improves product performance as well as prioritizes both consumer and environmental well-being [187].

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